

Optimized Multiplier based upon 6-Input Luts and Vedic Mathematics

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Abstract—A new approach has been used for optimized design of multipliers based upon the concepts of Vedic mathematics. The design has been targeted to state-of-the-art field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs). The multiplier generates partial products using Vedic mathematics method by employing basic 4x4 multipliers designed by exploiting 6-input LUTs and multiplexers in the same slices resulting in drastic reduction in area. The multiplier is realized on Xilinx FPGAs using devices Virtex-5 and Virtex-6. Carry Chain Adder was employed to obtain final products. The performance of the proposed multiplier was examined and compared to well-known multipliers such as Booth, Carry Save, Carry ripple, and array multipliers. It is demonstrated that the proposed multiplier is superior in terms of speed as well as power consumption.

Keywords—Multiplier, Vedic Mathematics, LUTs, FPGAs.

I. INTRODUCTION

A multiplier is a part of a processor that is widely used in digital devices such as computers, laptops, mobile phones, and so forth. It plays an important role in digital signal processing (DSPs) and image processing. Thus, the multipliers which have high speed and low power consumption are important.

For the last several decades, many attempts have been made by various researchers to develop algorithms for multipliers' design, which have high speed as well as low power consumption. However, to meet both these specifications simultaneously has been difficult. Some algorithms are suitable to design high speed multipliers, while others are appropriate for reducing area usage.

A number of multipliers such as Braun, parallel, column bypass, and carry ripple multipliers [1], [2] are slow multipliers. However, they use less area in ASIC or FPGAs implementation and power consumption is low. On the other hand, booth and Karatsuba-based Montgomery multipliers [3] are high speed multipliers with extra area used as a coding hardware. These multipliers are often used in applications requiring high speed. In the present work, an attempt is made to design a multiplier based on Vedic mathematics and exploiting 6-input LUTs of Xilinx FPGAs such that the two specifications, high speed and low power consumption are simultaneously met.

Besides speed and power issues in selecting an algorithm to design a multiplier, technology implementation is becoming the next issue.

There are two well-known technologies to realize hardware namely ASIC and FPGAs. ASIC is a full custom design,

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where a designer must arrange all modules on transistor level.

The ASIC technology provides high performance but has several disadvantages as given below:

- The integrated circuit costs are rising aggressively.
- ASIC complexity has lengthened development time.
- R&D resource and headcount are decreasing.
- Revenue losses for slow time-to-market are increasing.
- Financial constraints in a poor economy are driving low-cost technologies.

These trends make FPGAs a better alternative than ASIC for a large number of even higher-volume applications than they have been historically used for. Further, it is well established that full custom ASICs are the most expensive to manufacture and design and have the largest turn-around time. Thus they are preferred only when [4]:

1. There are no suitable existing cell libraries available which may be used for entire design, i.e. the cells are not small or fast enough or consume much power.
2. The ASIC technology is new or so specialized.

Therefore, FPGAs are selected for implementation of the optimized multiplier based on Vedic mathematics.

II. FPGA BASED MULTIPLIERS

As the rapid development on FPGA's technology, designing a low power and fast multiplier based upon FPGA is becoming realistic. A number of multipliers based on FPGAs have been realized.

Mangal et al.[5] introduced a technique of insertion of more zeros in the multiplicand to reduce switching activity and power consumption. Several advantages of this scenario are: first, average logic-switching-frequency is low; second, logic switching at each edge clock is decreased; finally, lowering capacitance of the routing network especially at high frequency. The design shows an improvement in power dissipation. However, the power reduction takes place only when a bit zero is available in the multiplicand. In addition to reducing power, a condition, where zero in the multiplicand is present in most of the time, is required. This situation is difficult to find in real life applications, where bits in the multiplicand are interchangeable between zeros and ones.

Similar work was done by Bhattacharjee, Basak, and Chakrabarti [6], who evaluated a number of multipliers in order to find out the most appropriate arithmetic circuits for FPGA, based DSP realization. The work indicated that among the six tested multipliers; Carry Save Multiplier (CSM) was the most suitable circuit for FPGA based DSP implementation. However, there are several reasons, why the result is not acceptable for DSP realization: firstly, it is not enough to evaluate only six types of multipliers to find out the most

Fig. 2 8x8 proposed multiplier

B. Subgroup Multiplier

Arrangement of a block circuit or a sub block circuit within the same slice or CLBs is very important in FPGAs design. A number of advantages can be achieved with this scenario: first, the routing process becomes faster; second, time delay is minimized; finally, the performance of the circuit is enhanced.

Fig. 3 depicts Configurable Logic Blocks (CLBs) and slices of Virtex-5 Xilinx FPGA. Each CLB contains two slices. Each slice consists of four 6-input LUTs, four flip-flops, and supported logic circuitry such as MUXF7, MUXF8, and dedicated XOR gates (not shown in the Fig).

One of the new features of Virtex-5 is the availability of 6-input LUTs where designers are able to design a circuit having six inputs with one level logic.

Previous generations of FPGAs with 4-input LUTs takes two level logics to design 6 input circuits, for example. In addition, Virtex-5 and the latest generations of FPGAs are fabricated with new technology yielding better performance compared to the old generations. Hence, Virtex-5 devices are used for the present design.

The proposed subgroup multiplier is depicted in Fig. 4. This sub multiplier involves two 4-bit operands (eight *inputs*- X_0, X_1, X_2, X_3 , and Y_0, Y_1, Y_2, Y_3), and eight outputs ($P_0, P_1, P_2, \dots, P_7$).

The first three outputs are simply attained by exploiting only LUTs, while other five outputs require Multiplexers, MUXF7 and MUXF8 as indicated in the Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Virtex-5 CLB and Slice [14]

Fig. 4 4x4 multiplier based LUTs

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed Vedic multiplier and its corresponding blocks are described using structural Verilog-HDL and synthesized employing Xilinx Synthesis Tool (XST), WebPACK version 13.3. The implementation was targeted to Xilinx Virtex-5, device XC5VLX30. From the implementation results as indicated in Table I, it is found that the proposed 8x8 multiplier has a delay which is roughly half of the other six multipliers reported in [6]. In the case of the occupied area, the proposed design comprises about 23 slices, which is slightly larger than CSM design.

Moving to higher multipliers, Fig. 5 shows the histogram stating the proposed 16x16 multiplier (PM) that offers high speed with delay less than half of the other multipliers except CSM and BSM III. In terms of the occupied slice, it shows a small increase compared to CSM and BSM II.

TABLE I
 OCCUPIED SLICES AND MAXIMUM DELAYS

Multiplier width	Multiplier type	Delay (ns)	No. of slices
8 x 8	Basic Multiplier	15.67	30
	Carry Save Multiplier	8.90	21
	Carry Ripple Multiplier	14.08	23
	Boot Sign Multiplier I	16.64	35
	Boot Sign Multiplier II	11.56	23
	Boot Sign Multiplier III	11.52	26
	Proposed Multiplier	6.59	23

Fig. 5 Delay and area comparison of 16x16 multipliers

A sharp increase in delays occurs at 32x32 multipliers as described in [6]. It is almost double compared to 16x16 multipliers. In contrast, with the proposed Multiplier, only a small, insignificant increase in delay is found which is about 4.8 ns as can be seen in Fig. 6. In the case of area occupation, PM places middle position among of the multipliers. It is fair to sacrifice small slices to achieve the best performance.

Fig. 6 The association of area and delay in 32x32 multipliers

To ensure that the hardware implementation works properly, simulation test was performed using ISim (O.76.xd). Fig. 7 indicates the post-route simulation result of the proposed multiplier. The test was done for different bit width, starting with 8x8, 16x16, and 32x32 bits. For convenience, the decimal number is used for displaying digit inputs and outputs of the hardware.

Fig. 7 Simulation result of the proposed multiplier

Another implementation was also done for Virtex-6, device XC6VLX75T. Although the FPGA's generations and the device categories are diverse, a comparison of the proposed multiplier with Virtex-5 implementation is described to get a brief view of the different technology's realization. Fig. 8 illustrates the variation of delays when PM was implemented on Virtex-6 and Virtex-5. From the histogram, it can be seen that the delays are slightly lower in Virtex-6 compared to Virtex-5. In addition, the area occupation of both implementations is shown in Table II. Even though the area occupation looks closed to each other, the physical area is much more on Virtex-5 compared to Virtex-6. This is understandable since Virtex-5 is fabricated using 65nm technology where as Virtex-6 is fabricated with 40nm technology [15], [16].

Fig. 8 Maximum delays on Virtex-5 and Virtex-6

TABLE II
 OCCUPIED SLICES ON VIRTEX-5 AND VIRTEX-6

Multiplier width	Multiplier type	Virtex-5	Virtex-6
8 x 8	Proposed Multiplier (PM)	24	25
16 x 16		105	108
32 x 32		433	439

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new approach for design and hardware realization of multipliers based upon the concept of Vedic mathematics. The technique is applied on sub-multiplication blocks, which are the fundamental blocks of the Vedic multiplier. The sub-multiplication blocks are optimized by employing 6-input LUTs and multiplexers within the same slices or CLBs. By setting placement and design goal strategies, the results of the proposed multiplier show better performance in terms of speed compared to the multipliers reported in literature. In terms of the device utilization also, in most of the cases studied, better results are obtained. Finally, it may be mentioned that in the present work hardware realization is based on FPGAs. It is suggested that the proposed multiplier technique may be considered for transistor level optimization using full-custom implementation in order to get the best performance.

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